

Design of Concrete Encased Composite Columns According to The General Method (prEN1994-1-1)

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ABSTRACT

Eurocode 4 provides two methods for the verification of structural stability of the composite columns in steel and concrete: the simplified methods and the general method. The simplified methods have a limited scope of application related to the geometry and material parameters of steel and concrete. In engineering practice, these limitations are often exceeded and also the application of high strength materials become more important. On the other hand, the general method can be applied in any type of composite without those limitation, but as a method is more complex and more sophisticated, as the design is based on geometric and material non-linear analysis with imperfections (GMNIA), considering all the physical and material nonlinearities such as geometric imperfection, residual stresses, local instability, cracking of the concrete, yielding of the structural steel and reinforcements. The current Eurocode 4: EN 1994-1-1 includes this advanced design method but does not provide detailed information on how to apply it. However, the second draft of Eurocode 4: prEN 1994-1-1 fills this gap by explaining the application of this method in more detail. This paper is focused on the general method and demonstrates the application of the general method for composite columns in steel and concrete subjected to compressive force by case studies. In the main part of the paper, the buckling resistance of columns based on general and simplified method are compared considering different column lengths (relative slenderness $\bar{\lambda}$). Furthermore, different geometric imperfections are applied for this case study as they are currently under review by standard bodies. Moreover, the N-M interaction diagram evaluated with plastic and strain-limited resistance to determine the overall safety factor γ_0 necessary for the general method is presented.

Keywords: composite columns, general method, plastic resistance, strain-limited resistance

1 INTRODUCTION

In accordance with EN 1994-1-1 (1), the cross-section resistance of the composite column subjected to only axial compression force is simply the sum of the plastic resistance of the concrete, steel, and reinforcement. On the other hand, the resistance of the cross-section in the case of compression force and bending moment is determined through the development of the N-M interaction diagram using plastic or nonlinear (strain-limited) resistance. Regarding the stability problem, the slenderness (λ), which is typically correlated with column length, is the primary factor that determines a composite column's resistance to eccentric or centric force as the stability check against buckling becomes more crucial with the increase of the column's length.

EN 1994-1-1 (1) proposes two principal methods for assessing the structural stability of steel and concrete composite columns against buckling: the general method and the simplified methods. The application of the simplified methods is restricted to steel and concrete material parameters, limited geometry, and slenderness (1), (10), while the general method is applicable also for composite compression member not fulfilling all these conditions. However, the

general method requires an advanced knowledge and experience for nonlinear numerical design, as it is based on geometric and material nonlinear analysis considering initial imperfections (GMNIA). EN 1994-1-1 (1) only provides very limited guidance for the application of the method. Nevertheless, the draft of second generation for Eurocode 4: prEN 1994-1-1 (3) closes this gap and provides a more detailed explanation on how to use this method.

2 STRUCTURAL STABILITY ACCORDING TO EN 1994-1-1

2.1 The simplified method (European buckling curves) for axial loading

The simplified stability proof in EN 1994-1-1 (1) permits simple member verification. In accordance with (1), for stability check of the composite columns in steel and concrete subjected to compression force without eccentricity the following equation need to be satisfied:

$$\frac{N_{Ed}}{\chi \cdot N_{pl,Rd}} \leq 1 \quad (1)$$

where N_{Ed} stands for the design compressive force, $N_{pl,Rd}$ is the plastic resistance of the cross-section given in (1), Equation (6.33) and χ is the reduction factor due to the buckling effect which is linked to relative slenderness ratio $\bar{\lambda}$ calculated as:

$$\chi = \frac{1}{\phi + \sqrt{\phi^2 - \bar{\lambda}^2}} \quad \text{but } \chi \leq 1 \quad (2)$$

where ϕ is called intermediate factor in accordance with EN 1993-1-1 (2), calculated as:

$$\phi = 0.5 \cdot [1 + \alpha \cdot (\bar{\lambda} - 0.2) + \bar{\lambda}^2] \quad (3)$$

where α is the imperfection factor given in EN 1993-1-1 (2), Table 6.1, while relative slenderness $\bar{\lambda}$ is calculated as:

$$\bar{\lambda} = \sqrt{\frac{N_{pl,Rk}}{N_{cr}}} \leq 2.0 \quad (4)$$

where $N_{pl,Rk}$ is the plastic resistance of the cross-section in the characteristic values for materials, and N_{cr} is the elastic critical load or so-called Eulerian buckling load defined as:

$$N_{cr} = \frac{(EI)_{eff} \times \pi^2}{L_e^2} \quad (5)$$

where $(EI)_{eff}$ is effective flexural stiffness of the cross-section calculated according to (1), Equation (6.40) and L_e is the effective length of the column.

2.2 The general method (prEN 1994-1-1)

The general method is based on non-linear finite element analysis known as GMNIA. It is a sophisticated method that demands a significant amount of computational time and effort. It accounts for all nonlinearities related to material and geometry present in the composite column members, including geometric imperfection, residual stresses, local buckling, concrete

cracking, steel, reinforcement yielding, and long-term effects on concrete. The general method consists of two steps (7). The first step is the nonlinear numerical analysis (GMNIA), while in the second step, the overall (safety) factor γ_0 is calculated from the N-M interaction curve based on nonlinear resistance (strain-limited) or plastic resistance on the cross-section level.

2.2.1 Nonlinear finite element analysis (GMNIA)

The incremental non-linear finite element analysis needs to account for the initial geometric imperfections, residual stresses on the steel section, and non-linear material stress-strain curves constructed using the mean values for the concrete, steel, and reinforced bars based on prEN1992-1-1 (4) and prEN1993-1-14 (5). *Figure 1* illustrates how the material stress-strain curves in the GMNIA are based on mean values, and the obtained resistance R_m and corresponding displacement w_m represent the average load-bearing capacity and displacement of the column.

Figure 1. Geometric and Material Nonlinear Analysis with Imperfections (GMNIA)

An important discussion came up within the development of the 2nd generation of Eurocode 4 related to the geometric imperfection. Current EN 1994-1-1 (1) does not provide any information on it. Considering literature (10) and (13) as a reference, a magnitude of $w_0 = L/1000$ is proposed for composite column which is also presented in prEN1993-1-14 (5) for steel columns. In fact, the geometric imperfection for concrete encased composite columns is resulting from several effects, installation tolerances (positioning of formwork, steel-profile, reinforcement) and non-straightness or twist of the cross-section members (14). Due to the complexity and different materials involved, it is not possible to accurately determine every imperfection along the length of the columns after the concrete has been cast, and as a result, a numerical calibration is necessary. Nevertheless, this recalculation may include the problem that the restoring moments due to the friction and rotation stiffness of the supports are often unknown or not documented, consequently effects resulting from buckling length and imperfection cannot be clearly separated. Newer investigation (12) proves for slender concrete encased composite column a more important geometric imperfection closer to those of reinforced concrete columns in accordance with Eurocode 2.

Currently, the geometric imperfection for composite columns is under review by the standard committee. For composite columns an initial geometrical imperfection between $L/400$ and

$L/1000$ may be applied, while a higher magnitude is more suitable for concrete encased column. By the presented case study, the results for the initial imperfection of $L/1000$ (13), $L/660$ (12) and $L/400$ (4) are compared to spot out the significance.

Regarding the residual stresses on steel profile, for considered HEB 160 – S355 hot-rolled section, a triangular distribution with maximum magnitude based on steel grade S235 according to prEN1993-1-14 (5) is used. However, as it is reported in (9) the impact of residual stresses on flexural buckling of CEC columns subjected to compression force is insignificant.

2.2.2 Determination of the overall safety factor γ_0

The resistance R_m determined in the FE analysis should be decreased by the overall (safety) factor γ_0 in line with Eq. (6) in order to obtain the design load resistance required for the design of composite columns.

$$R_d = \frac{R_m}{\gamma_0} \quad (6)$$

where:

$$\gamma_0 = \frac{R_m^{\rightarrow}}{R_d^{\rightarrow}} \quad (7)$$

With reference to *Figure 2*, the overall (safety) factor γ_0 is computed using the N-M interaction diagram based on plastic resistance (continuous line) or strain-limitation (dashed red line) using the mean and the design values for material parameters at the cross-section level. Current EN 1994-1-1 (1) includes only plastic resistance. However, for a sophisticated method it seems to be more appropriate to use the nonlinear resistance also describing better the cross-section resistance as it is shown in *Figure 2*. Therefore, the draft prEN1994-1-1 (3) explicitly allows the use of plastic or strain-limited N-M interaction curve. The mean and the design strength for concrete, steel and reinforcement are given in prEN1992-1-1 (4) and prEN1993-1-14 (5).

Figure 2. Determination of the overall safety factor γ_0

The bending moment and the external compression force determine the direction of the resistance vectors $R_{pl,d}$ and $R_{pl,m}$. However, the mean resistance obtained from GMNIA R_m^{GMNIA} (see *Figure 1*) and the corresponding second-order moment M_x^{II} due to axial compressive force given in Eq. (8) may be used to determine the vector's direction in the case

where the maximum load bearing resistance is to be determined. Where the proof is to be provided for a certain load combination, the second-order moment can be determined by the acting normal force and the deformation resulting from the GMNIA.

$$M_x^{II} = R_M^{GMNIA} \cdot (w_{0,x} + w_{m,x}) \quad (8)$$

Where $w_{0,x}$ is the initial geometric imperfection and $w_{m,x}$ is the maximum displacement at the column's midspan determined from GMNIA. To display the outcomes of the general method in terms of *European buckling curves*, the reduction factor χ is computed as follows:

$$\chi = \frac{R_d}{N_{pl,Rd}} \quad (9)$$

where R_d is the design resistance calculated according to Eq. (6) and $N_{pl,Rd}$ is the plastic resistance of the cross-section given in (1).

3 APPLICATION OF THE GENERAL METHOD – CASE STUDY

3.1 Geometry and model

Figure 3 presents the cross-section, material parameters, and boundary conditions of the concrete encased composite (CEC) columns used in the present study. The geometry of the composite columns is adopted from (12). However, the material parameters have been changed to normal strength material and the loading is considered as axial loading without any eccentricity causing flexural buckling around the weak axis (z-z). Idealized simple supported boundary conditions are used, with the objective to cover all of the column relative slenderness in the range between $0.2 \leq \bar{\lambda} \leq 2.0$ as the analyses were carried out by varying the column's length.

There are two reasons for basing the case study on the geometry of the documented experiments reported in (12): firstly, the possibility for calibration of the FE-model, and secondly, the geometric imperfections have been recalculated in (12) so that their influence can be compared with approaches given by the literature.

Figure 3. Material parameters, boundary conditions, and cross-section of the CEC columns

The open-source commercial finite element program OpenSees (7), which can perform both linear and non-linear static analysis using scripting languages like Python, was used in this study. The results from Geometric and Material Non-linear Analysis with Imperfection (GMNIA) in OpenSees (7) models are validated with a 3D model in ABAQUS (6) in order to guarantee that the self-developed Python model in OpenSees (7) provides trustworthy computational results. Whereas reported in (9), the ABAQUS model was benchmarked with CEC slender columns tests in (12) under biaxial loading.

As the application of biaxial moments is not possible in the OpenSees (7), a direct benchmark for those tests could not be provided. The primary benefits of OpenSees (7) over ABAQUS (6) are the reduced analysis time and the ability to conduct parametric analyses which were required for the present study. Additional information regarding the OpenSees and ABAQUS model and modelling methodology can be found in (9).

Furthermore, the concrete contribution of the section is very high and determining for the failure. Therefore, an important difference between plastic and strain-limited resistance can be detected on cross-section level. It is to be mentioned that concrete encased circular cross-section cannot be verified according to the simplified method EN1994-1-1 (1) and prEN1994-1-1 (3), therefore the general method is required for the design. Also, the square section does not fulfil the boundary conditions related to the concrete cover demanded by EN1994-1-1 (1) for the application of the simplified method.

Figure 4. Stress-strain material law for steel (left side) and concrete (right side) in OpenSees (7)

The FE-model used in (7) to produce non-linear analysis is based on the so-called distributed plasticity (fibre method), which permits the plasticity to be spread and allows yielding to occur at any part of the element (11). The following assumptions are made to apply the fibre method for composite columns: section remains plane after deformation, non-linear stress-strain material law, full interaction between steel and concrete, the imperfections are taken into account, the confinement effect in concrete is considered, the tensile strength of concrete is considered but only for the numerical analysis not for the following determination of the cross-section resistance by the N-M interaction curves. It is to be mentioned that for engineering design unfavourable effects resulting from creep and shrinkage are to be considered. However, here only the analyses without consideration of those effects are presented. In reference to the materials, the OpenSees (7) library contains a number of material models for steel and concrete. Giuffre-Menegotto-Pinto, a uniaxial stress-strain material with isotropic strain hardening, is used for structural steel and reinforcement bars (7), while for concrete, two material models were employed: the confined concrete, which was used for the concrete inside the reinforcement cage, and the standard uniaxial Popovics concrete material with tensile strength (7). Figure 4 shows the stress-strain material law used in OpenSees (7) for steel and concrete.

Regarding the initial geometric imperfection and residual stresses, the initial geometric imperfection is taken into account by "shifting" the nodes on the OpenSees model from their original positions following the half-sinusoidal shape, with the maximum amplitude at the mid-length as it is presented in *Figure 5*, while the initial stress condition command available in OpenSees (7) is used to consider the effect of the residual stresses on the steel profile by applying stresses along the normal direction on the web and flanges (9).

Figure 5. Initial geometrical imperfection (out-of-straightness) (adopted from (9))

3.2 Nonlinear analysis by OpenSees and ABAQUS

The GMNIA is the first step for the general method and as mentioned before, the ABAQUS model was benchmarked by comparison with experimental test data for slender columns under compression and biaxial bending reported in (12). As the biaxial bending cannot be arranged with the OpenSees, the validated 3D Abaqus model for same column under axial loading is compared to the results of GMNIA in OpenSees (7) for this case study. In order to validate OpenSees with ABAQUS, the material parameters based on mean values, boundary conditions, and cross-section of the CEC column displayed in *Figure 3* are selected and the column's length, $L = 6300 \text{ mm}$, is adopted.

Figure 6 shows the results of the GMNIA by the load-displacement curve in OpenSees (7) and ABAQUS (6) for considered CEC columns with an initial imperfection $w_0 = L/1000$ (solid lines). As the difference in resistance is less than 3% for both columns, the results demonstrate a good agreement between the ABAQUS and the OpenSees model. To provide information about reduction of the resistance when applying a geometric imperfection of $L/660$ (12) and $L/400$ (4) respectively, the load-deflection curves by OpenSees are also printed in *Figure 6* (dashed lines), showing a reduction of the resistance about 5% for $L/660$ and about 15% for $L/400$.

Figure 6. Comparison of the load-displacement curves based on mean values in ABAQUS (6) and OpenSees (7) for CEC columns with $L_{cr} = 6.30 \text{ m}$ and initial imperfection $L/1000$, $L/660$ and $L/400$

3.3 Analysis results

The outcomes of the simplified method (*European buckling curves*) for CEC columns are compared with the results of the general method conducted in OpenSees (7) for the previously mentioned initial imperfections.

Figure 7 and Figure 8 present the findings of GMNIA for the rectangular and circular concrete encased composite (CEC) columns described above.

The results are visualised in a non-dimensional form, utilizing relative slenderness $\bar{\lambda}$ and reduction factor χ , and are intended to verify the flexural buckling around the weak axis (z-z). The design resistance is calculated using the general method with an overall factor γ_0 based on the plastic N-M interaction diagram. For the analysis based on the initial imperfection of $L/1000$ the overall factor γ_0 is also computed based on the nonlinear (strain-limited) N-M interaction curve. In general, for buckling about the weak axis (z-z) rectangular CEC column sections are assigned to the *buckling curve c* in accordance with EN 1994-1-1 (1), while the circular CEC column sections are without any reference regarding the *European buckling curve*. The plots resulting from the general method are displayed in Figure 7 and Figure 8 (left side).

Figure 7. Rectangular CEC column according to the general method buckling about the weak axis (z-z)

Figure 8. Circular CEC column according to the general method buckling about the weak axis (z-z)

The first finding is the good agreement for the overall factor γ_0 computed using the nonlinear (strain-limited) and plastic resistance. Even if the N-M interaction diagrams show important differences for plastic and nonlinear resistance, the impact on the overall factor is very low as presented by Figure 7 and Figure 8 (right side, compare blue and red curves). The overall factor γ_0 based on plastic resistance is slightly more conservative while the effect is decreasing

with the increase of the columns length. A more detailed scientific validation regarding the difference between the plastic and strain-limited N-M interaction diagram is presented in (9). On the other hand, the impact of the applied initial imperfection is spotlighted. For the presented columns, applying an initial imperfection of $L/1000$ leads to a major consistency with *buckling curve a*, while an initial imperfection of $L/660$ shows a compliance with *buckling curve b* and the highest initial bow imperfection of $L/400$ results to an overlapping with *buckling curve c* dropping to *curve d* for high slenderness. The following differences in the resistance may be summarised for the investigated case study compared to $w_0 = L/1000$ as:

- Columns length up to 5 m: reduction by 5% for $L/660$ and 12% for $L/400$
- Columns length up to 8 m: reduction by 7% for $L/660$ and 9% for $L/400$
- Columns length over 8 m: reduction by 10% for $L/660$ and 25% for $L/400$ (for the presented column those lengths are not relevant anymore).

Moreover, due to the very low steel contribution (δ) and high concrete strength (C50/60), the concrete column behaviour becomes closer to a reinforced concrete column. While the classification to the *European buckling curves* (a_0, a, b, c, d) were initially created for steel columns, and these curves consider the effects of both the initial geometric imperfection and the residual stresses (equivalent imperfection). However, as demonstrated in (9), the residual stresses have an insignificant effect on the buckling resistance of the CEC composite columns with high concrete contribution. Therefore, for CEC columns with low steel contributions, in the Eurocode 4 EN 1994-1-1 (1) affiliation to the *European buckling curves* provide conservative results.

4 SUMMARY

The present article focuses on the general method, explaining the methodology, input data and changes provided in the draft of second generation prEN1994-1-1. Further a case study is investigated for the application of the general method for circular and rectangular CEC columns subjected to centric compression force. Thereby, different initial geometric imperfections have been applied. The overall factor required to compute the design resistance in the general method is calculated based on plastic and strain-limited resistance N-M interaction diagram, while only minor differences could be determined. Based on the design resistance, the columns have been assigned in accordance with the European buckling curves. The comparison underlines the importance of the geometric imperfection for the general method as this can lead to an overestimation of the column's resistance or very conservative results. Eurocode 4 should provide clear guidance for the geometric imperfection in order to provide the structural engineer reliable assumptions for the design.

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